

Electroorganic synthesis of esters and ketones at the platinum anode in aqueous medium

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Abstract : Electroorganic synthesis of esters from the saturated primary aliphatic alcohols and ketones from the secondary aliphatic alcohols have been carried out in electrooxidation at the platinum anode in aqueous medium. This is an important reaction because of high oxidation potential of alcohols. Electrochemical oxidation has been carried out under controlled potential electrolysis at room temperature in a three electrode cell assembly containing two platinum electrodes in the form of square plates as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The structures of compounds were confirmed from the IR, NMR, mass spectral and microanalyses. The products formed during the electrooxidation of ethanol, propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 2-butanol and *sec*-butyl alcohol are reported here.

Keywords : Electrochemical oxidation, controlled potential electrolysis, platinum electrode, green chemistry.

Introduction

The oxidation of aliphatic saturated alcohols into the aldehydes, ketones and carboxylic acids are achievable with a general oxidizing reagent^{1,2}. But the direct anodic oxidations of aliphatic saturated alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds are not always achievable³, since direct oxidation of alcohols is difficult due to higher oxidation potential. The reaction is just different from the conventional oxidation of primary alcohols where aldehydes and carboxylic acids were obtained as the oxidation product. Here we are reporting the result of our studies on the electrooxidation of some primary and secondary aliphatic alcohols viz. ethanol, propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 2-butanol and *sec*-butyl alcohol. Four corresponding esters in the electrooxidation of primary alcohols and ketones from the secondary alcohols were obtained at the platinum electrode during controlled potential electrolysis^{4,5}.

Results and discussion

The direct oxidation of alcohols is generally best achieved by using acetonitrile as the solvent and a fluoroborate as the supporting electrolyte. Though, such

direct oxidation is not always most effective method to oxidize general aliphatic alcohols. 77% yield was obtained in the oxidation of 1-butanol by using a platinum anode and lithium tetrafluoroborate as a supporting electrolyte in the presence of 10% acetonitrile produced the best result⁶.

The active species are generally generated by the direct electron transfer between substrate and electrode in the electroorganic reactions. Hence the formation of active species is generally controlled by the oxidation and reduction potentials of the substrates. When these potentials are beyond the range accessible by the usual electrochemical techniques, direct electron transfer between the substrate and electrode hardly takes place as in the direct oxidation of aliphatic saturated alcohols. Therefore it is necessary to discuss some other methods to oxidize and reduce the substrate. Also even if the accessible range of electrochemical method, it is more desirable that the substrates are oxidized or reduced at much lower potentials than those applied in the direct method. This is achieved by using mediators. The oxidative reaction system using a mediator, which is called as mediatory system, is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of mediatory system in the electrooxidation of alcohols.

The oxidation potential of the substrate *S* in the figure is beyond the range accessible by the direct electrochemical method so that electron transfer from *S* to the anode hardly occurs, and also the high oxidation potential necessary for the direct oxidation of *S* may cause unexpected side reaction involving oxidation of the solvent or supporting electrolytes. However, when a compound M_{Red} (a reduced form of Mediator KI denoted by *M*) which is oxidized at a lower potential than *S*, is added to the reaction system, the oxidation of M_{Red} to M_{Ox} (an oxidized form of *M*) will take place prior to the oxidation of *S*. M_{Ox} is able to oxidize *S* to the product *P*, the oxidation of *S* with *M* may be effected in two ways, namely by direct electron transfer (homogeneous electron transfer) from *S* to *M* in solution or by chemical oxidation of *S* with M_{Ox} . The former system is called as homomediatory system and the later is a heteromediatory (or chemomediatory) system. The compound *M* is called a mediator or an electron carrier, since *M* mediates electron transfer between *S* and the anode.

When M_{Ox} oxidizes *S* in solution, M_{Ox} is reduced to M_{Red} which is again oxidized at the anode to regenerate M_{Ox} . Thus, if the lifetime of the redox system $M_{\text{Ox}} \leftrightarrow M_{\text{Red}}$ is sufficiently long, only a catalytic amount of mediator is required to promote the entire reaction.

In the heteromediatory system, the substrate is not oxidized by direct electron transfer from *S* to M_{Ox} but also by chemical reaction between *S* and M_{Ox} . Many of the mediatory systems which are useful in organic synthesis may be classified in this category. Although some electrochemical indirect oxidations using metal ions as the oxidizing agent have been known as rather classical type of mediatory systems. The most promising systems are those using new types of mediators which may not commonly be known as oxidizing agents in the usual

chemical methods. Among a variety of mediators, the redox system consisting of a halide anion and a positive halogen species is one of the most interesting mediator used in the organic synthesis. One of the earliest synthetic reactions in which the halide anion was used as a mediator is the anodic methoxylation of furan in the presence of 0.05 equivalents, though the reaction has not been called a mediated oxidation⁷.

Alcohols have been widely used as solvents for anodic alkoxylation for Kolbe reactions and as solubilising components with water. Reaction of alcohols in aqueous systems has been studied in detail because of their possible utilization in fuel cell technology. However, the reactions of alcohols in an inert system under controlled conditions have not been studied. The cathodic reaction would involve hydrogen discharge, analogous to the water reaction with the potential determined by the acidity of the alcohol. This reaction does not occur for the methanol, ethanol or cyclohexanol in the potential range available in either acetonitrile or dimethylformamide⁸⁻¹⁰. In fact these compounds serve as electrochemically inert proton donors in these solvents. Although when used as solvents, the available potential range of simple alcohols is not very great, attempts to observe the oxidation of methanol or ethanol by cyclic voltammetry at platinum anodes with sodium perchlorate supporting electrolyte in the acetonitrile were unsuccessful. There was indication of absorption of ethanol, but not of oxidation. The anodic reactions of variety of aromatic and aliphatic carbinols were studied by Lund¹¹. Experiment involved an acetonitrile-sodium perchlorate solution and platinum anodes, where most aromatic compounds were reactive within the potential range accessible in this system.

As discussed above the direct oxidation of alcohols is not always easy owing to their high oxidation potential. On the other hand, alcohols are easily oxidized by using the halogen ion redox system as the mediatory system.

When primary alcohols are oxidized in this mediatory system, the products are the corresponding esters. While the secondary alcohols evolve corresponding carbonyl compounds as shown in the Scheme 1.

The mechanism of oxidation of alcohols in the mediatory system will be as follows in Scheme 1 and Scheme 2.

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Scheme 1. Electrooxidation of primary and secondary alcohols.

Scheme 2. Mechanistic proposal for electrooxidation of primary alcohols.

Scheme 3. Mechanistic proposal for electrooxidation of secondary alcohols.

The oxidation of alcohols in a cooled cell with a water jacket has been carried out at constant current through the two phase solution with vigorous stirring.

Here the important point of our electrochemical study is that the reaction takes place at room temperature at the

controlled potential. The potential range for the electrolysis of different compounds is 0.5 to 2.0 V, but the specific potential for the reaction from various observations is found to be approximately 1.00 V vs Hg/Hg²⁺. Total 2.0-3.5 F mol⁻¹ of electricity was passed for the elec-

tolysis which is very small in comparison to the energy used in other conventional methods. Besides these merits it is an important fact that no chemical reaction gives such esters by using alcohols only. It is possible only in this electrochemical method.

Experimental

Analysis and measurements : Column chromatography was carried out by using Merck silica gel 60. The purity of the synthesized compounds were ascertained by TLC on precoated silica gel plates in various solvent systems using iodine vapors and UV light as detecting agent. Infra red spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets and reported in cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured on Bruker DRX 300 MHz FT spectrometer instruments using $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent with TMS and CDCl_3 as internal standards (chemical shift in δ ppm). Carbon multiplicities were assigned by DEPT techniques. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and were recorded on an Elementar Vario EL III. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values. Mass spectra were taken out on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6600 mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon (6 KV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. All the chemicals used were of synthetic and AR grade and was procured from Agros-Organics, USA, S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Mumbai and Merck, Mumbai, India.

General experimental procedure :

Reaction solution : The reaction solution was prepared by adding the 0.1 M solution of alcohol with (83 g) 0.01 M potassium iodide in the 50 mL water. Potassium iodide is used as supporting electrolyte as well as mediator in the reaction.

Electrolysis : Preparative scale controlled potential electrolysis¹²⁻¹⁶ was performed at room temperature in a three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate¹⁷⁻¹⁹ as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. All the electrolysis experiments were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potentials and were completed in 3 h. After 3 h no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. All the products were light colored liquid and entirely different from the starting compounds. The current potential data was recorded with the help of potentiostat at the interval of 15 min and has been tabulated as Table 1.

Extraction : The products were extracted from the reaction solution to chloroform layer by the simple solvent extraction technique after diluting the reaction solution with double distilled water. Two-immiscible layers of water and chloroform were shaken in a separatory funnel and allowed to settle down. After some time the chloroform layer containing the desired product was removed. The extracted chloroform layer was left over-

Table 1. Current-potential data as recorded by potentiostat

Sl. no.	Current (mA)					
	Ethanol	Propanol	1-Butanol	1-Pentanol	2-Butanol	sec-Butyl alcohol
1.	852	823	980	1080	988	845
2.	791	742	925	1015	935	807
3.	753	694	857	962	859	791
4.	722	659	799	935	797	744
5.	685	608	741	910	752	729
6.	654	565	684	876	703	708
7.	609	514	613	845	641	682
8.	548	472	558	820	570	666
9.	516	423	485	785	497	645
10.	444	367	410	760	434	628
11.	397	275	365	735	376	605
12.	360	260	350	700	352	585
Applied potential (V)	1.00	0.85	1.25	1.50	2.00	1.50

CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.48 (2H, quartet, J 7.3 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.12 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.07 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz, CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 206.9 (C=O), 67.9 (CH₂CH₃), 30.6 (CH₃), 13.7 (CH₂CH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 73 (M⁺ + 1) (exact mass : 72.11) (Found : C, 66.32; H, 11.05. Calcd. for C₄H₈O : C, 66.67; H, 11.11%).

3-Methyl-2-butanone (g) : Yield 4.36 g (87%), b.p. 94–95 °C, IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3007 (C–H str), 2940 (C–H), 1717 (C=O str), 1450, 1410 and 1372 (C–H), 1365 (C–H def); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 4.12 (2H, septet, J 7.3 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.38 (6H, d, J 7.3 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.12 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 206.5 (C=O), 30.5 (CH₃), 25.8 (CHCH₃), 13.7 (CH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 87 (M⁺ + 1) (exact mass : 86.13) (Found : C, 69.45; H, 11.35. Calcd. for C₅H₁₀O : C, 69.77; H, 11.62%).

Conclusion :

It is obvious from the above studies that the electrochemical oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols provides a good method for the oxidation which is not so easy by chemical method as the no chemical method evolves an ester from the alcohols only and the oxidation of secondary alcohols into ketones requires a strong oxidizing reagent. Here only potassium iodide was used as mediator as well as supporting electrolyte. Thus the reaction evolves the products in excellent yield by the oxidation on the platinum electrode. Therefore the method is simple and ecofriendly and hence a part of green chemistry.

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References

1. I. L. Finar, "Organic Chemistry", Eastern Press Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, 2000.
2. A. Bahal and B. S. Bahal, "A Textbook of Organic Chemistry", S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi, 2006.
3. T. Shono, "Electroorganic Synthesis", Academic Press Ltd., London, 1991.
4. C. K. Mann and K. K. Barnes, "Electrochemical Reactions in Non-aqueous Systems", Marcel Dekker, Inc, New York, 1970.
5. A. J. Fry, "Synthetic Organic Electrochemistry", Wiley Interscience Publication, New York, 1989.
6. P. C. School, S. E. Lentsch and Van De Mark, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, **32**, 303.
7. N. Kass-Clauson, F. Limborg and K. Glens, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, **06**, 531.
8. P. H. Given and M. E. Peorer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **25**, 385.
9. P. Yousefzadeh and C. K. Mann, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **33**, 2716.
10. T. Shono, Y. Matsumura, J. Hayashi and M. Mizoyachi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, **19**, 165.
11. H. Lund, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 491.
12. L. K. Sharma, S. Kumar, P. Yadav and R. K. P. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 1277.
13. K. L. Yadav, S. Kumar, A. Kumar and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 595.
14. S. Kumar and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 934.
15. K. L. Yadav, A. Kumar, S. Kumar and R. K. P. Singh, *Transactions of the SAEST*, 2005, **40**, 106.
16. A. Kumar, S. Kumar and R. K. P. Singh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 2005, **75A IV**, 233.
17. S. Singh, S. Kumar, L. K. Sharma and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 734.
18. S. Kumar, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **53**, 159.
19. S. Kumar, S. Singh and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 1145.